

SNHL in Diabetics: A Prospective Study

Vivek V Harkare, Nitin V Deosthale, Sonali P Khadakkar, Priti R Dhoke, Kanchan S Dhote, Ashish Gupta

Department of ENT, NKP Salve Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Centre & Lata Mangeshkar Hospital, Nagpur

(Received: June, 2012)

(Accepted: May, 2014)

ABSTRACT:

The aim of this study was to assess the hearing threshold level in patients of diabetes mellitus, correlate degree of hearing loss with duration and severity of hyperglycemia and complications of diabetes mellitus. This prospective longitudinal study was carried out from November 2007 to October 2009. Patients of previously diagnosed cases of diabetes mellitus below 60 years of age were subjected to fasting and post-meal blood sugar levels and Pure Tone Audiometric tests. Seventy four percent diabetics were affected with sensorineural hearing loss. There was no statistically significant association between the age and the sex of diabetic patients with hearing loss. The results showed bilateral significantly high frequency, mild to moderate sensorineural hearing loss in uncontrolled diabetics as compared to those with controlled diabetes ($p=0.001$). Diabetics with poorly controlled blood sugar level have increased risk of hearing loss.

KEY WORDS: Diabetes Mellitus, pure tone audiometry, Sensorineural Hearing Loss (SNHL).

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder, due to relative or absolute lack of insulin, which results in elevated blood sugar levels. Morbidity in Diabetes Mellitus is mainly due to long term micro and macro vascular complications affecting blood vessels of eyes, kidneys, heart and nerves. The relationship between diabetes mellitus and hearing loss has been debated for many years. It has been postulated that the microvascular & neuropathic complications of diabetes do affect the hearing of individuals. Studies in diabetic animals have demonstrated thickening of the basement membrane of capillaries of striavascularis.^[1]

Diabetes mellitus has been implicated as independent causative factor of sensorineural hearing loss. Most audiometric studies of hearing in patients of diabetes show a mild to moderate sensorineural hearing loss mostly in high frequency^[2], although Celik et al^[3] noted high threshold at all frequencies tested in diabetics.

In view of contradictory results regarding hearing impairment in diabetic patients, we designed this prospective study with the objectives to assess the hearing threshold level in diagnosed patients of diabetes mellitus, to study the correlation between the degree of hearing loss and the duration, severity of hyperglycemia and its complications.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

This was a prospective study carried out from November 2007 to October 2009. Institutional Ethical Committee approval was taken for the study. Total 100 patients who had already been diagnosed as Diabetes mellitus based on recommendation of National Diabetic Data Group of National Institute of Health were included in the study. The patients included in this study were diabetic patients of any gender with age below 60 years. Insulin and/or oral glucose lowering agents were used to control diabetes in those cases. Exclusion criteria included diabetic patients above 60 years, habit of smoking, alcohol consumption, previous or current ototoxic drug intake, associated ear diseases, MMR infection, Goitre, Tuberculosis, Noise Induced Hearing loss and pregnant females. Those 100 patients included 50 cases of controlled disease group

Corresponding Author: Dr. Vivek Vishwas Harkare, 20, 'Mahurgad' Sawarkar Nagar, Khamla Road, Nagpur
Phone No.: +91 09422105174
E-mail: viv_harkare@rediffmail.com

(Fasting blood sugar- 80-140 mg/dl, Post-meal blood sugar-110-180 mg/dl, Urine sugar- Nil) and 50 cases of uncontrolled disease group (Fasting Blood Sugar- 128-452 mg/dl, Post-meal blood sugar-190-500 mg/dl, Urine Sugar- 0.5- 2%).

Detailed history including age, gender, duration of diabetes mellitus, type of diabetes and previous medical history were noted. Detailed systemic examination to rule out any diabetic complications was done and ENT examination was carried out by the specialist. Fasting and Post-meal Blood Sugar levels were determined by Glucose Oxidase method with the help of "Selectra-E" machine. Pure Tone air and bone-conduction thresholds were obtained by using 'Elkon Digital Audiometer EDA Giga 3'. Type and severity of sensorineural hearing loss was classified.

Data was analyzed using chi-square, Odds Ratio and were considered significant if p value is less than 0.05. It was done by using Epi Info software version 3.4.3.

RESULTS:

This study was carried out in 100 cases who were already diagnosed as having diabetes mellitus. Elderly diabetics were affected more with sensorineural hearing loss than young age group (Table I). But there was no statistically significant association between age of diabetic and incidence of hearing loss (p value - 0.98). Male: Female ratio in a study group was 2:1 (66 males, 34 females). 72.72% male diabetics were having sensorineural hearing loss while 70.58% female diabetics were affected with sensorineural hearing loss. This indicates that, there was no significant association between the sex of diabetics and hearing loss. In the current study, 3 out of 5 Type I diabetic patients had sensorineural hearing

loss while 71 out of 95 Type II diabetics were showing sensorineural hearing loss. This shows no significant difference in hearing loss among Type I & Type II diabetics.

There was definite influence of blood sugar level on hearing [Table 2]. Uncontrolled diabetic patients with high blood sugar levels (88%, 44/50) had higher rate of sensorineural hearing loss when compared to that of controlled diabetic patients with normal blood sugar level (60%, 30/50). This difference is highly statistically significant (p value =0.001 & Odds Ratio = 4.89).

Comparison of duration of diabetes with incidence and severity of sensorineural hearing loss was done [Table 3]. Those who had diabetes more than 10 years had higher incidence of sensorineural hearing loss (92.85%, 13/14) than those with diabetes less than 10 years (70.93%, 61/86). But there was no statistically significant association between the two.

Table 4 compares the hearing loss between the diabetics with complications and without complications. Sixty seven patients of diabetes mellitus had one or more complications like retinopathy, neuropathy, nephropathy, non-healing ulcers etc while 33 diabetics were unaffected of complications. Statistical association between diabetics with complications and sensorineural hearing loss was found to be highly significant (p=0.000004 and Odds Ratio = 11.63).

The analysis of air and bone conduction thresholds of right and left ear of all diabetics at different frequencies were made. The audiograms of the diabetic patients had no significant air-bone gap. The hearing loss was bilateral sensorineural type with mild to moderate degree. Higher frequencies (above 2000Hz) were affected more [Table 5 & 6].

Table 1- Type and severity of Sensorineural Hearing Loss in patients of various age groups of Diabetes Mellitus.

Age in years	Cases	Normal hearing	Sensorineural Hearing Loss				Total
			Mild 20-40db	Mod. 41-55db	Mod.Severe 56-70db	Severe 71-90db	
10-20	9	2	6	1	0	0	7
21-30	17	5	5	6	1	0	12
31-40	20	5	3	9	3	0	15
41-50	25	8	2	9	4	2	17
51-60	29	6	4	12	5	2	23
Total	100	26	20	37	13	4	74

$X^2=0.000$, p value=1

Table 2: Hearing loss at Different Blood Glucose levels.

Group	Fasting Blood Glucose Level	No. of Diabetic Cases	Normal Hearing	Sensorineural Hearing Loss				Total
				Mild 20-40db	Mod 41-55db	Mod. Severe 56-70db	Severe 71-90db	
Controlled Diabetes (50)	80-140mg/dl	50	20	13	15	2	0	30
	140-200mg/dl	26	4	5	14	2	1	22
Uncontrolled Diabetes(50)	201-300mg/dl	10	2	2	3	2	1	8
	301 mg/dl & above	14	0	0	5	7	2	14

$X^2= 10.19$, p value =0.001 (significant) , Odds Ratio =4.89

Table 3: Hearing loss in accordance with duration of Diabetes.

Duration of diabetes in year	No. of Diabetes cases	Normal hearing	Sensorineural Hearing Loss				Total
			Mild 20-40dB	Mod. 41-55dB	Mod. Severe 56-70dB	Severe 71-90dB	
Group I <5 years	46	14	15	15	2	0	32
Group II 5-10 years	40	11	5	17	6	1	29
Group III >10 years	14	1	0	5	5	3	13

$X^2=1.2$, p value =0.29

Table 4: Hearing loss in diabetic cases with and without complications.

Diabetic cases	Sensorineural Hearing loss	Normal Hearing	Total
With complications	60	7	67
Without Complications	14	19	33
Total	74	26	100

$X^2= 25.52$, p value = <0.0001 (significant) , Odds Ratio = 11.63

Table 5: Association of Sensorineural Hearing Loss at different Bone Conduction Threshold with controlled and uncontrolled Diabetic Group.

Group of Diabetics	Cases with low frequency loss (<2000Hz)	Cases with High frequency loss (>2000Hz)	Total Cases
	Controlled	17	
Uncontrolled	15	29	44
Total	32	42	74

$X^2= 3.70$, p value = 0.054

Table 6: Association of Sensorineural Hearing Loss at Different Air conduction thresholds with controlled and uncontrolled Diabetic Group.

Group of Diabetics	Cases with low frequency loss (<2000Hz)	Cases with High frequency loss (>2000Hz)	Total
	Controlled	14	
Uncontrolled	17	27	44
Total	31	43	74

$X^2= 0.47$, p value = 0.49

DISCUSSION:

It is evident from a review of otolaryngology literature that the relationship between diabetes and sensorineural hearing loss is complex. In the current study, hearing status in patients with diabetes mellitus was evaluated. It shows that 74.07% diabetics had sensorineural hearing loss [Table 1]. Friedman et al^[4], showed a 55% incidence of hearing loss in diabetic patients. Weng et al^[5] noted that, 44.8% diabetic subjects had profound hearing loss, while Rajendran et al^[6] showed 73% diabetic patients having sensorineural hearing loss.

Age is another variable that could play a role in hearing loss. Axelsson et al^[7] showed that the incidence of pure tone hearing loss increases with age in patients with diabetes, even after correction for senile deafness. In the present study also incidence of sensorineural hearing loss was increased with the age of diabetics. However, there was no significant association between age and sensorineural hearing loss (p value 0.98). In our study, males with sensorineural hearing loss (72.72%) were slightly more as compared with females (70.05%). (Data not depicted in Tables). Cullen and Cinnamon^[8] found that male diabetics had worse hearing than female patients with diabetes.

The duration of diabetes in relation to hearing loss has also been investigated with no clear association (p value 0.29). Celik et al^[3] observed that as the duration of diabetes increased to 15 years, incidence on hearing loss also increased. After 15 years of diabetes, the influence on hearing loss was not significant.

There was a significant association between blood glucose level and sensorineural hearing loss (p value 0.001) in the present study. All 14 patients who had blood glucose level above 301 mg/dl were having sensorineural hearing loss (100% incidence). Sixty percent controlled diabetics had sensorineural hearing loss while 88% uncontrolled diabetics had sensorineural hearing loss. Kurien et al^[9] carried out the study on 30 diabetic cases & found that there was maximum incidence of sensorineural hearing loss of high frequency when blood glucose level was higher than normal.

There was strong association between diabetic complications and sensorineural hearing loss (p value <0.01) in our study. Diabetics with one or more complications had high incidence of sensorineural hearing loss (60 patients out of 67) than those without diabetic complications (14 patients out of 33). Kurien

et al^[9] also found that patients without complications had relatively lower level of sensorineural hearing loss as compared to patients with diabetic complications. Taylor and Irwin^[10] reported that almost 70% of their adult diabetics had hearing impairment. This occurred more commonly when retinopathy was present. Parving A^[11] in his study of 20 patients with diabetic microangiopathy did not find correlation between hearing impairment and angiopathy as well as neuropathy. Hearing loss in diabetic patients in the current study was pure sensorineural hearing loss. Audiograms of those patients had no significant Air-Bone gap. Hearing loss was more in higher frequencies. This result was supported by previous studies.^[3,6,8] But Fagcho Ma et al,^[12] and Friedman et al^[4] observed the strongest association of hearing loss at lowest frequency at 500Hz. However, in our study, it was observed that, more number of patients (Total 42) were having higher frequency sensorineural hearing loss (> 2000Hz).

CONCLUSION:

The diabetic subjects had higher hearing threshold with bilateral mild to moderate degree sensorineural hearing loss. Age, gender of diabetic patient and duration of diabetes had no significant correlation with hearing loss. Since blood glucose level and diabetic complications had strong association with sensorineural hearing loss. Diabetic patients with poor control of blood glucose level have increased risk of hearing loss and may be an under diagnosed complication of diabetes.

While considering sensorineural hearing loss to be a consequence of diabetes, a metabolic assessment may be useful for patients presenting with hearing loss so as to reduce the high rate of undiagnosed diabetes mellitus in the community. On the other hand, routine screening for hearing loss in diabetes patients may also be helpful to diminish comorbidities among them and improve their quality of life.

REFERENCES:

1. Jorgensen MB, Buch NH. Studies on inner ear function and cranial nerves in diabetics. *Arch Otolaryngol* 1961;74:373-381.
2. Harner SG. Hearing in adult onset diabetes mellitus. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 1981;89:322-7.
3. Celik O, Yalcin S, Celebi H, Ozturk A. Hearing loss in

- insulin- dependent diabetes mellitus. *Auris Nasus Larynx* 1996;23:127-32.
4. Friedman SA, Schulman RH, Weiss S. Hearing and diabetic neuropathy. *Arch Intern Med* 1975;135(4):573-6.
 5. Weng SF, Chen YS, Hsu CJ, Tseng FY. Clinical features of sudden sensorineural hearing loss in diabetic patients. *Laryngoscope* 2005;115(9):1676-80.
 6. Rajendran S, Anandhalakshmi, Mythili B, Viswanatha Rao. Evaluation of incidence of sensorineural hearing loss in patients with type2 diabetes mellitus. *Int J Biol Med Res* 2011;2(4): 982-87.
 7. Axelsson A, Sigroth K, Vertes D. Hearing in diabetics. *Actaotolaryngol* 1978;356 (Suppl):3-21.
 8. Cullen JR, Cinnamond MJ. Hearing loss in diabetics. *J Laryngol Otol* 1993;107:179-82.
 9. Kurien M, Thomas K, Bhanu TS. Hearing threshold in patients with diabetes mellitus. *J Laryngol Otol* 1989;103(2):164-68.
 10. Taylor IG, Irwin J. Some audiological aspects of diabetes mellitus. *J Laryngol Otol* 1978;92:99-13.
 11. Parving A. Hearing problems and hormonal disturbances in the elderly. *Act Otolaryngol Suppl (Stockh)* 1990;476:44-3.
 12. FangchaoMa, Orlando Gomez-Marin, LeeDJ, Balkany T. Diabetes and hearing impairment in Mexican American adults: a population based study. *J Laryngol Otol* 1998;112:835-839.

Cite this article as: Harkare VV, Deosthale NV, Khadakkar SP, Dhoke PR, Dhote KS, Gupta A. A Prospective Study Hearing Status in Patients with Diabetes Mellitus. *PJSR*2014;7(2):38-2.

Source of Support: Nil, **Conflict of Interest:** None declared.